

مقومات الصحة النفسية لدى مستخدمي الإنترنت في ضوء بعض المتغيرات الديموغرافية: إدمان الإنترنت الإيجابي مدخل مقترح للعلاج النفسي

Mental Health Components among Internet Users in Light of Some Variables: Positive Internet Addiction as a Proposed Psychotherapy Approach

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ملخص:

هدف هذا البحث التعرف إلى مستوى مقومات الصحة النفسية لدى مستخدمي الإنترنت، والكشف عن الفروق في مقومات الصحة النفسية تبعاً لتأثير الجنس وعدد ساعات استخدام الإنترنت وعدد مواقع التواصل الاجتماعي المستخدمة والفئة العمرية وكذلك الغرض من استخدام الإنترنت. وذلك على عينة تكونت من (317)، (111 ذكر، 206 إناث) من مستخدمي الإنترنت، طبق عليهم استمارة بيانات ديموجرافية ومقياس مقومات الصحة النفسية الذي أعدته الباحثة بعد التحقق من خصائصه السيكومترية. وقد أسفرت نتائج التحليل الإحصائي عن وجود مستوى مرتفع من مقومات الصحة النفسية. كما وجدت فروق دالة إحصائياً بين متوسطات درجات أفراد عينة البحث في مقومات الصحة النفسية (الدرجة الكلية- الأبعاد) باختلاف الجنس وعدد ساعات استخدام الإنترنت وعدد مواقع التواصل الاجتماعي المستخدمة والفئة العمرية وكذلك الغرض من استخدام الإنترنت.

الكلمات المفتاحية: مقومات الصحة النفسية، مستخدمي الإنترنت، إدمان الإنترنت الإيجابي، مدخل مقترح للعلاج النفسي.

Abstract:

This study aimed to identify the level of mental health components of internet users, and to detect the differences in the components of mental health due to demographic variables. The sample comprised 317 (111 males and 206 females) of internet users. A demographic data checklist and mental health scale (prepared by the researcher) was used after verifying its psychometric characteristics. The results of the statistical analysis revealed a high level of mental health among internet users. There were also statistically significant differences between the average scores of internet users in the components of mental health (total degree and dimensions) due to the variable of gender, number of hours of internet use, number of social networking sites used and age group, as well as the purpose of using the internet.

Keywords: Mental Health Components, Internet users, Positive Internet Addiction, Proposed Mental Therapy.

Theoretical Background

The current century is known as the «age of the information revolution», which has contributed to social communication, cultural and knowledge exchange among individuals anywhere in the world. As a result of the availability of the internet and the vast amount of information, individuals of different ages, education, income use the internet. A person may use the internet for reading, knowledge, social communication, entertainment, education, training, online shopping, receiving specific counseling and for psychotherapy services.

The widespread of information, cultural and cognitive openness contributed to the process of cultural, cognitive and social exchange, increased acquaintance and social integration. Hence, the interest of researchers in revealing the motives and effects of using the internet. Majali's study (2007) indicates that the impact of internet use increases if students use the internet on their own, and found that the internet is used for scientific and research purposes. As for the motives for using the internet, the results of Mansour's (2004) study found that the first motivation for using internet is to seek knowledge, followed by fun, recreation and social relationships. The study of Taya (2000) found that 72.6% of the respondents use the internet as an important source of information at 91.5%, entertainment and leisure time at 88.7% and as a means of communicating with others at 59.3%. The results of the Abdul Salam study (1998) revealed that 72.7% of the sample decided that they use the internet to access information and entertainment by 47%, making friends by 42.3%, curiosity and love by 25.5%. It explained that the older the user of the internet is, the less entertainment and recreation was sought.

The world unsettling turmoil nowadays, have a fast and strong impact on the mental health of the individual, and impose more psychological, social and economic stress on the individual and the family, increasing the need for counseling services. On the other hand, these events of violence, crimes, terrorism, wars and conflicts have led humans to lose the feeling of safety.

The use of online social networking, has made it possible to communicate with anyone

anywhere in the world and at any time, which in return can have an impact on the individual's well-being and mental health. A person characterized with positive mental health is identified by Zahran (2005) as a person who possesses personal and social compatibility, a sense of happiness with the self and with others, self-realization, and ability to cope with the demands of life.

Mental health is the network between the sound, mental, emotional, personal, social and self-realization factors. The correlation between the cognitive factors, such as intelligence, the ability to think, creativity and academic achievement on the one hand, and the emotional factors, personal and social values on the other, lead to responses indicating the individual's quest realize him/herself and raises the level of personal and social consensus. The individual who possesses these characteristics is the one characterized by a sound mental health (Khalidi, 2002).

The absence of psychological disorder does not mean a sound mental health. The standard of personality integration is the regularity of its components and different characteristics, since the integrated personality is the normal personality (Abdullah, 2008).

In the recent years, researchers have focused on studying the negative effects of internet use on mental health. Indeed, many studies have shown the negative effects of internet use on individuals of different ages. The study of Al-Kandari and Al-Qashan (2001) showed that there was a relationship between the time of internet consumed and social isolation. The study of Ayazra and Al-Malki (2017) aimed to detect the effect of using internet on the level of depression among university students. The study revealed that there was a high level of depression among students who used the internet. The results also showed that the depression increases, the more hours students use the internet.

However, this study sheds lights on the effects of internet use, and detects the negative effects of internet on mental health. The ICD and the DSM have not yet included internet use as a mental disorder. This, in my view, may be due to the benefits and positive effects of internet use on the human health.

Few studies have demonstrated that the benefits of using internet in education, such as the study of Al-Hilaa (2000) had an effect on the academic achievement. As for the internet use's positive effects on mental health, the use of internet as a counseling and therapeutic approach for psychological problems, drew little attention. Shaw and Gant's (2002) study found that self-esteem and social support increased with the use of the internet, while the loneliness decreased. The studies showed that there was a statistically significant positive correlation between the number of hours of social networking and psychological well-being such as study of Charlimoragn and Cotton, 2003; Kalpidus, Costin and Morris, 2011; Chen, 2012; Chan, 2015; Wang, Chau and Stefanone, 2015. A few number of studies have focused on the positive impact of using the internet as an approach to counseling and psychotherapy of mental health problems.

In his book «Positive Addiction» published in 1985, Glasser said in regards to positive addiction «there are a few positive addictions in the lives of individuals, such as reading, meditation, yoga, reading and others». Positive addiction increases strength and satisfaction with life. Glasser said that these positive addictions are completely opposite to the negative addictions, such as alcohol or heroin addiction that will weaken and destroy the strength of the individual. Despite the novelty of the term at present, the applications of positive addiction in psychology do not yet exist. Thousands of people have positive addiction, many of whom see it as strong habits, but few realize that these strong habits are addictive. It is called positive addiction, because of its addictive nature. These addictions are usually stronger than those negative addictions. As a result of this power, individuals live with greater self-confidence, more creativity, happiness, and often better health (Glasser, 1985).

Nevertheless, Glasser argue that anything we do for an hour a day at least six days per a week, takes about six months to be labeled as addictive. One of the activities that an individual is addicted to is the use of the internet. Studies of Azab, 2001; Arnout, 2006; Al-Qarni, 2011; Sheikh, 2011; Al-Hantouchi, 2010; Al-Qarni, 2011; Al-Tarawneh and Al-Fneikh, 2012; and Al-Goma, 2014 have

shown the use of internet as a negative addiction. There has been a correlation between internet addiction and aggression, introversion, anxiety, depression, aggression, personality disorder, mental, psychopathy, paranoia, neurosis, solitude and isolation.

About negative addiction, Glasser also mentioned that there exists three types of choices of weaknesses an individual can choose to deal with during the process of his/ her life. The first is the choice of giving up. This indicates that something is wrong, and the individual feels helpless and incapable of change. If the individual does not have the strength to change, he/ she becomes stuck with the pain, and as a result, the individual feels weak and begins to give up. The second choice is to classify the symptoms, that may be mild as headaches or intense as severe depression which lead to suicide. When the individual chooses to surrender, he/she retains the pain, and moves on to the second option to show pathological symptoms. The third choice is passive addiction, which is the worrying step. It is difficult to break this addiction because it is strong. This causes unhappiness, which makes individuals weak and prone to losing happiness (Glasser, 1985).

Glasser (1985) pointed out that one of the problems he tried to solve as a psychiatrist, is how to teach people ways to help themselves to grow better. The stronger they become, the more likely they will cope effectively with life's stress to be happier. Positive addiction provides an effective way for most people to grow stronger. Glasser emphasized that the concepts of positive addiction are especially useful for those counselors who want to teach their clients to help themselves directly. In my opinion, the more we expand our way of knowledge in this matter, the more likely we are to be effective in our treatments.

It is clear from the above that the psychotherapy of modern trends have become a necessity of contemporary life. Thus, it is possible to device activities and tasks within programs that decrease psychological problems. Through these programs, we can strengthen the personality of the individual, as a counseling and psychotherapy approach. This can be achieved through the use

of internet, without encountering mental illness stress and focusing on competing. For one hour a day and for at least six days a week throughout the period of six-months, the individual can use the internet without stressing out for doing so, with belief that the use of the internet can improve his/ her life and and achieve physical, psychological, social and spiritual benefits.

The importance of this study lies in addressing the use of the internet in the light of positive psychology. It also focuses on its potential role in the counseling and psychotherapy of some problems and mental disorders, as well as the possibility of using internet as a strategy to cope with life stresses and improve mental health, which may contribute to enriching the theoretical heritage of counseling and psychotherapy, by identifying the mental health components of internet users.

Method

Respondents

Internet users comprised 111 men and 206 women, their ages ranged between 17-45 years, with mean ages of 30.08 years. Participants provided written informed consent and completed the study questionnaires online.

Materials and Procedure

Preliminary data form (Prepared by the researcher), that included items on gender and age, number of hours of internet use, number of social networking sites used, and internet usage.

Components of mental health scale

The researcher prepared a scale of the components of mental health which consists of 50 sentences evenly distributed on five dimensions, each dimension consisted of 10 sentences. Responses are distributed on a Likert scale with 1 (never) to 5 (very often). The psychometric characteristics of the mental health component were calculated on a sample of 80 internet users. The internal consistency of the scale was strong. Results found that the correlation coefficients of

the sentences to the total degree of the dimension to which they belong were statistically significant, ranged from 0.520 to 0.872, and the correlation coefficients of the sentences to the overall score of the scale were statistically significant, ranging from 0.449 to 0.824. The reliability of the mental health scale was verified, by the alpha-Cronbach. Results showed that the dimensional correlation coefficients in the overall degree of the scale were statistically significant, as they ranged between 0.850 to 0.931, indicating internal consistency of the scale.

Analysis

Preliminary analyses included descriptive statistics, t-test, and ANOVA for test differences. in components of mental health. Data was examined for adherence to assumptions and the alpha level

was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

As hypothesized, there is an average level of mental health components among internet users. In order to verify this hypothesis, the mean was calculated and compared to test the value. Results showed that the total score of mental health components was high with a mean of 189.559, which is greater than the test value of 150 and a standard deviation of 57.456. The sub-dimensions of the mental health components were also high with a mean of 38.498, 38.274, 37.817, 37.782, 37.186 respectively which is also higher than the test value of 30 and a standard deviation of 12.570, 12.810, 11.716, 11.695, 10.074 respectively. The value of "t" for one independent group was statistically significant.

Table 1.
One- sample test

measure	M	Test value	SD	t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Mindfulness	38.498	30	12.038	12.570	0.000
Psychological resilience	38.274	30	11.500	12.810	0.000
Self-efficacy	37.817	30	11.879	11.716	0.000
Social support	37.782	30	11.848	11.695	0.000
Happiness	37.186	30	11.659	10.974	0.000
Mental health components	189.599	150	57.456	12.258	0.000

The second hypothesis states that «there are no statistically significant differences between the males and females in mental health scores.» To verify this hypothesis, the means were calculated, and t-test was tested, results showed that there are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of males and females in the components of mental health for dimensions and total score in favor of females. The mean scores in these five dimensions and the total score (44.563, 44.048, 44.001, 43.956, 43.374, 219.915 respectively), were higher than the male means in the same dimensions (26.400, 26.790, 25.200, 25.143, 24.543, 128.076 respectively).

Table 2.
Differences in the components of mental health between males and females internet users

measure	Groups	N	M	SD	t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Mindfulness	male	111	26.400	9.353	17.645	0.000
	female	206	44.563	8.167		
Psychological resilience	male	111	26.790	7.891	17.445	0.000
	female	206	44.048	8.427		
Self-efficacy	male	111	25.200	7.371	19.709	0.000
	female	206	44.009	8.241		
Social support	male	111	25.143	7.1285	19.894	0.000
	female	206	43.956	8.245		

measure	Groups	N	M	SD	t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Happiness	male	105	24.543	6.614	20.681	0.000
	female	206	43.374	8.045		
Mental health components	male	105	128.076	35.364	20.085	0.000
	female	206	219.951	39.485		

The third hypothesis stated that “there is no statistically significant effect of the number of hours of internet use on the mental health components.” To verify this hypothesis, the ANOVA analysis was used to detect the significance of differences between internet users’ mean scores of 1-3 hours, internet users of 4-6 hours, and internet users of more than 6 hours on mental health components for dimensions and total score. The results showed that there were statistically significant differences in mental health components dimensions and total score for mindfulness, psychological resilience, self-efficacy, social support, happiness and total score of mental health components among internet users due to the number of internet usage hours. The differences were in favor of internet users of 3-6 hours.

Table 3.

Differences in the components of mental health due to number of hours of use

measure	Groups	N	M	SD
Mindfulness	1.00	64	33.344	13.20800
	2.00	116	42.509	9.71372
	3.00	137	37.511	12.20241
	Total	317	38.498	12.03782
Psychological resilience	1.00	64	33.937	11.93484
	2.00	116	42.422	9.65505
	3.00	137	36.788	11.69366
	Total	317	38.274	11.50029
Self-efficacy	1.00	64	32.922	11.84464
	2.00	116	42.379	9.33032
	3.00	137	36.241	12.55958
	Total	317	37.817	11.87906
Social support	1.00	64	32.547	11.60313
	2.00	116	42.353	9.70455
	3.00	137	36.358	12.30360
	Total	317	37.782	11.84766
happiness	1.00	64	31.734	11.91004
	2.00	116	41.802	9.57281
	3.00	137	35.825	11.77416
	Total	317	37.186	11.65919
total	1.00	64	164.484	58.97268
	2.00	116	211.465	46.56747
	3.00	137	182.723	58.93625
	Total	317	189.558	57.45621

Table 4.

Differences in the mental health components of Internet users due to the number of hours of Internet users

measure		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Mindfulness	Between Groups	3699.587	2	1849.793	13.799	0.000
	Within Groups	42091.662	314	134.050		
	Total	45791.249	316			
Psychological resilience	Between Groups	3502.210	2	1751.105	14.360	0.000
	Within Groups	38290.913	314	121.946		
	Total	41793.123	316			
Self-efficacy	Between Groups	4288.417	2	2144.209	16.706	0.000
	Within Groups	40302.971	314	128.353		
	Total	44591.388	316			
Social support	Between Groups	4456.139	2	2228.069	17.534	0.000
	Within Groups	39899.842	314	127.070		
	Total	44355.981	316			
happiness	Between Groups	4627.299	2	2313.650	18.954	0.000
	Within Groups	38328.720	314	122.066		
	Total	42956.019	316			

Table 5.

“Scheffe” results

Dependent Variable			Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Mindfulness	1.00	2.00	-9.16487-*	1.80281	0.000
		3.00	-4.16720-	1.75300	0.061
	2.00	1.00	9.16487*	1.80281	0.000
		3.00	4.99767*	1.46085	0.003
	3.00	1.00	4.16720	1.75300	0.061
		2.00	-4.99767-*	1.46085	0.003
Psychological resilience	1.00	2.00	-8.48491-*	1.71949	0.000
		3.00	-2.85082-	1.67198	0.235
	2.00	1.00	8.48491*	1.71949	0.000
		3.00	5.63409*	1.39333	0.000
	3.00	1.00	2.85082	1.67198	0.235
		2.00	-5.63409-*	1.39333	0.000
Self-efficacy	1.00	2.00	-9.45744-*	1.76409	0.000
		3.00	-3.31900-	1.71534	0.156
	2.00	1.00	9.45744*	1.76409	0.000
		3.00	6.13843*	1.42947	0.000
	3.00	1.00	3.31900	1.71534	0.156
		2.00	-6.13843-*	1.42947	0.000

Dependent Variable			Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Social support	1.00	2.00	-9.80657-*	1.75525	0.000
		3.00	-3.81079-	1.70674	0.084
	2.00	1.00	9.80657*	1.75525	0.000
		3.00	5.99578*	1.42230	0.000
	3.00	1.00	3.81079	1.70674	0.084
		2.00	-5.99578-*	1.42230	0.000
happiness	1.00	2.00	-10.06735-*	1.72034	0.000
		3.00	-4.09044-	1.67280	0.052
	2.00	1.00	10.06735*	1.72034	0.000
		3.00	5.97691*	1.39402	0.000
	3.00	1.00	4.09044	1.67280	0.052
		2.00	-5.97691-*	1.39402	0.000
total	1.00	2.00	-46.98114-*	8.52351	0.000
		3.00	-18.23825-	8.28798	0.090
	2.00	1.00	46.98114*	8.52351	0.000
		3.00	28.74289*	6.90672	0.000
	3.00	1.00	18.23825	8.28798	0.090
		2.00	-28.74289-*	6.90672	0.000

The fourth hypothesis stated that “there is no statistically significant effect on the number of social networking sites used on the mental health components of internet users.” To verify this hypothesis, the means were calculated by using t-test, networking sites used for those who use more than three sites, where the mean scores in these five dimensions and the total score were 43.525, 42.922, 42.776, 42.749, 42.256, 214.228 respectively, for males and the means in the same dimensions were 27.265, 26.880, 26.735, 26.684, 25.857, 134.429 respectively.

Table 6.

Differences in the components of mental health due to number of social media sites used

variables	Groups	N	M	SD	t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Mindfulness	Less (3) sites	98	27.265	11.72059	14.218	0.000
	More (3) sites	219	43.525	8.17431		
Psychological resilience	Less (3) sites	98	27.888	10.84937	13.490	0.000
	More (3) sites	219	42.922	8.31481		
more (3) sites	Less (3) sites	98	26.735	10.59328	14.212	0.000
	More ((3) sites	219	42.776	8.64277		
Social support	Less (3) sites	98	26.684	10.54651	14.306	0.000
	More (3) sites	219	42.749	8.59197		
Happiness	Less (3) sites	98	25.857	10.28060	15.222	0.000
	More (3) sites	219	42.256	8.15494		
Mental health components	Less (3) sites	98	134.429	52.33418	14.896	0.000
	More (3) sites	219	214.228	39.86092		

The fifth hypothesis stated that “there is no statistically significant effect on the mental health components of internet users.” To verify this hypothesis, ANOVA was used to detect the significance of the differences between the mean age of internet users by age group. They were divided into three psychological age groups of <20 years, 20-30 years, > 30 years (dimensions and total degree). The results showed that there were statistically significant differences in mental health components dimensions and the total-score for mindfulness, psychological resilience, self-efficacy, social support happiness and total score of mental health components among internet users due to the number of internet usage hours. The differences were in favor of the internet users who were over the age of 30 years, with mean scores in mental health (dimensions and total) levels of 41,603, 41,754, 40,809, 40,952, 40.929, 205,048 respectively of those under the age of 20, or between the ages of 20 and 30 years.

Table 7.

Mean and standard deviations of Internet users in mental health components due to age group

measure	Groups	N	M	SD
Mindfulness	1.00	40	38.5250	11.59130
	2.00	151	35.9007	12.90672
	3.00	126	41.6032	10.32673
	Total	317	38.4984	12.03782
Psychological resilience	1.00	40	37.3250	12.70652
	2.00	151	35.6225	12.03591
	3.00	126	41.7540	9.44177
	Total	317	38.2744	11.50029
Self-efficacy	1.00	40	37.3500	12.32373
	2.00	151	35.4437	12.71463
	3.00	126	40.8095	9.97253
	Total	317	37.8170	11.87906
Social support	1.00	40	37.6250	12.24470
	2.00	151	35.1788	12.85825
	3.00	126	40.9524	9.55729
	Total	317	37.7823	11.84766
happiness	1.00	40	37.3500	12.11600
	2.00	151	34.8543	12.65301
	3.00	126	39.9286	9.56927
	Total	317	37.1861	11.65919
total	1.00	40	188.1750	60.18471
	2.00	151	177.0000	61.55388
	3.00	126	205.0476	47.28346
	Total	317	189.5584	57.45621

1 refers to internet users with ages less than 20 years

2 refers to internet users with ages ranging between 20-30 years

3 refers to internet users with ages more than 30 years

Table 8.

Differences between the mean in the mental health components of Internet users due to age group

Variables	Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Mindfulness	Between Groups	2233.606	2	1116.803	8.051	0.000
	Within Groups	43557.644	314	138.719		
	Total	45791.249	316			
Psychological resilience	Between Groups	2623.492	2	1311.746	10.515	0.000
	Within Groups	39169.631	314	124.744		
	Total	41793.123	316			
Self-efficacy	Between Groups	1987.588	2	993.794	7.324	0.001
	Within Groups	42603.800	314	135.681		
	Total	44591.388	316			
Social support	Between Groups	2290.720	2	1145.360	8.550	0.000
	Within Groups	42065.261	314	133.966		
	Total	44355.981	316			
happiness	Between Groups	1769.767	2	884.884	6.746	0.001
	Within Groups	41186.252	314	131.166		
	Total	42956.019	316			
total	Between Groups	54120.681	2	27060.341	8.591	0.000
	Within Groups	989063.489	314	3149.884		
	Total	1043184.170	316			

Table 9.

“Scheffe” results

Dependent Variable	(I) age groups	(J) age groups	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Mindfulness	1.00	2.00	2.62434	2.09443	0.457
		3.00	-3.07817-	2.13750	0.356
	2.00	1.00	-2.62434-	2.09443	0.457
		3.00	-5.70251-*	1.42113	0.000
	3.00	1.00	3.07817	2.13750	0.356
		2.00	5.70251*	1.42113	0.000
Psychological resilience	1.00	2.00	1.70248	1.98613	0.693
		3.00	-4.42897-	2.02698	0.094
	2.00	1.00	-1.70248-	1.98613	0.693
		3.00	-6.13145-*	1.34765	0.000
	3.00	1.00	4.42897	2.02698	0.094
		2.00	6.13145*	1.34765	0.000
Self-efficacy	1.00	2.00	1.90629	2.07137	0.655
		3.00	-3.45952-	2.11397	0.264
	2.00	1.00	-1.90629-	2.07137	0.655
		3.00	-5.36582-*	1.40548	0.001
	3.00	1.00	3.45952	2.11397	0.264
		2.00	5.36582*	1.40548	0.001

Dependent Variable	(I) age groups	(J) age groups	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Social support	1.00	2.00	2.44619	2.05824	0.494
		3.00	-3.32738-	2.10056	0.287
	2.00	1.00	-2.44619-	2.05824	0.494
		3.00	-5.77357*	1.39657	0.000
	3.00	1.00	3.32738	2.10056	0.287
		2.00	5.77357*	1.39657	0.000
happiness	1.00	2.00	2.49570	2.03662	0.473
		3.00	-2.57857-	2.07850	0.464
	2.00	1.00	-2.49570-	2.03662	0.473
		3.00	-5.07427*	1.38190	0.001
	3.00	1.00	2.57857	2.07850	0.464
		2.00	5.07427*	1.38190	0.001
total	1.00	2.00	11.17500	9.98034	0.535
		3.00	-16.87262-	10.18559	0.255
	2.00	1.00	-11.17500-	9.98034	0.535
		3.00	-28.04762-*	6.77194	0.000
	3.00	1.00	16.87262	10.18559	0.255
		2.00	28.04762*	6.77194	0.000

The sixth hypothesis states that “there is no statistically significant effect in the use of internet on the mental health components of internet users. In order to verify this hypothesis, ANOVA was used to calculate the significance of the differences between the mean scores of internet users according to the purpose of the use of the internet. Those were divided into internet users for reading and knowledge, internet users for research and work, internet users for social communication in the components of mental health (dimensions and total degree). The results of the “Scheffe” comparisons between the mean scores of the members of the research sample via the components of mental health (dimensions and total score) according to the purpose of using the internet were verified. There were statistically significant differences in mental health components (dimension and total scores) among internet users due to the purpose of using the internet. The differences were in favor of internet users for the purpose of social communication.

Table 10.

Differences in mental health components (dimensions - total score) due to purpose of internet use

variables	Groups	N	M	SD	Std. Error
Mindfulness	1.00	62	29.9355	13.28116	1.68671
	2.00	85	37.2941	12.25894	1.32967
	3.00	170	42.2235	9.53955	.73165
	Total	317	38.4984	12.03782	.67611
Psychological resilience	1.00	62	30.6129	11.73527	1.49038
	2.00	85	36.9412	12.57961	1.36445
	3.00	170	41.7353	9.19000	.70484
	Total	317	38.2744	11.50029	.64592

variables	Groups	N	M	SD	Std. Error
Self-efficacy	1.00	62	30.5645	12.32034	1.56469
	2.00	85	35.5059	12.89760	1.39894
	3.00	170	41.6176	9.48002	.72708
	Total	317	37.8170	11.87906	.66719
Social support	1.00	62	30.2258	11.46830	1.45648
	2.00	85	35.4824	12.95377	1.40503
	3.00	170	41.6882	9.62445	.73816
	Total	317	37.7823	11.84766	.66543
happiness	1.00	62	29.8710	11.53112	1.46445
	2.00	85	35.0471	12.69130	1.37657
	3.00	170	40.9235	9.49432	.72818
	Total	317	37.1861	11.65919	.65485
total	1.00	62	151.2097	58.87111	7.47664
	2.00	85	180.2706	62.04173	6.72937
	3.00	170	208.1882	45.56847	3.49494
	Total	317	189.5584	57.45621	3.22706

1 refers to internet users for reading and knowledge

2 refers to internet user's for research and work

3 refers to internet user's for the social communication

Table 11.

Results of the analysis of the variance of the differences between the means in the mental health components due to the purpose of using the internet

variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Mindfulness	Between Groups	7028.354	2	3514.177	28.467	0.000
	Within Groups	38762.895	314	123.449		
	Total	45791.249	316			
Psychological resilience	Between Groups	5826.619	2	2913.310	25.434	0.000
	Within Groups	35966.504	314	114.543		
	Total	41793.123	316			
Self-efficacy	Between Groups	6170.752	2	3085.376	25.216	0.000
	Within Groups	38420.636	314	122.359		
	Total	44591.388	316			
Social support	Between Groups	6583.442	2	3291.721	27.364	0.000
	Within Groups	37772.539	314	120.295		
	Total	44355.981	316			
happiness	Between Groups	6081.234	2	3040.617	25.892	0.000
	Within Groups	36874.785	314	117.436		
	Total	42956.019	316			
total	Between Groups	157513.143	2	78756.572	27.922	0.000
	Within Groups	885671.027	314	2820.608		
	Total	1043184.170	316			

Table 12.
«Scheffe» results

Dependent Variable	(I) purpose of using Internet	(J) purpose of using Internet	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Mindfulness	1.00	2.00	-7.35863-*	1.85565	0.000
		3.00	-12.28805-*	1.64842	0.000
	2.00	1.00	7.35863*	1.85565	0.000
		3.00	-4.92941-*	1.47598	0.004
	3.00	1.00	12.28805*	1.64842	0.000
		2.00	4.92941*	1.47598	0.004
Psychological resilience	1.00	2.00	-6.32827-*	1.78747	0.002
		3.00	-11.12239-*	1.58784	0.000
	2.00	1.00	6.32827*	1.78747	0.002
		3.00	-4.79412-*	1.42174	0.004
	3.00	1.00	11.12239*	1.58784	0.000
		2.00	4.79412*	1.42174	0.004
Self-efficacy	1.00	2.00	-4.94137-*	1.84744	0.029
		3.00	-11.05313-*	1.64112	0.000
	2.00	1.00	4.94137*	1.84744	0.029
		3.00	-6.11176-*	1.46945	0.000
	3.00	1.00	11.05313*	1.64112	0.000
		2.00	6.11176*	1.46945	0.000
Social support	1.00	2.00	-5.25655-*	1.83179	0.017
		3.00	-11.46243-*	1.62722	0.000
	2.00	1.00	5.25655*	1.83179	0.017
		3.00	-6.20588-*	1.45700	0.000
	3.00	1.00	11.46243*	1.62722	0.000
		2.00	6.20588*	1.45700	0.000
happiness	1.00	2.00	-5.17609-*	1.80989	0.018
		3.00	-11.05256-*	1.60777	0.000
	2.00	1.00	5.17609*	1.80989	0.018
		3.00	-5.87647-*	1.43958	0.000
	3.00	1.00	11.05256*	1.60777	0.000
		2.00	5.87647*	1.43958	0.000
total	1.00	2.00	-29.06091-*	8.87002	0.005
		3.00	-56.97856-*	7.87944	0.000
	2.00	1.00	29.06091*	8.87002	0.005
		3.00	-27.91765-*	7.05517	0.000
	3.00	1.00	56.97856*	7.87944	0.000
		2.00	27.91765*	7.05517	0.000

Discussion

The results of hypothesis one are consistent with those results of Shaw and Gant (2002);

Charlimeragn and Cotton (2003); Kalpidus, Costin and Morris (2011); Chen (2012); Chan (2015); and Wang, Chau and Stefanone, (2015). The results show a positive impact on the use of the internet on mental health and the well-being. Thus, the internet users of the research sample obtained high scores for mindfulness, psychological resilience, self-efficacy, social support and happiness. The positive impact of the internet use, has become a necessity in all areas of life and an easy tool to use through time and space whenever the individual wants. This freedom, responsibility, sense of safety, satisfaction, and psychological resilience act as positive stimuli from a behavioral perspective that satisfies internet users' psychological and cognitive needs and makes them feel self-sufficient, when they receive the approval and acceptance of others. Thus, using the internet has become a pleasurable experience for them in order to express their emotions and thoughts without any restrictions. This finding can be explained in the light of the age group of internet users, the majority of whom are above the age of 20, where intellectual and psychological maturity, self-fulfillment, self-esteem and self-confident are developing.

This, in line with what Griffiths (1997) explained when stating that reliance on the internet is similar to the concept of positive addiction offered by Glasser for positive things such as exercise, meditation and yoga. It is also consistent with the results of Shotton's (1991) study that internet users have had a better level of academic performance.

Results also agree with the benefits of positive addiction, including the abandonment of bad habits, such as excessive drinking, anger and smoking, and increased mindfulness. Internet use increases self-awareness, well-being, self-confidence, tolerance, and positivity. Anyone needs a boost of positive strength from any positive addiction activity they engage in (Glasser, 1985). This boost empowers the individual with the elements needed for his/ her physical and psychological health, in terms of mindfulness, psychological resilience, self-efficacy and happiness, so to live an adequate and healthy life, which achieves internal and external balance and harmony in all spheres of life.

As for the hypothesis regarding the differences between males and females in mental health components, the results seem logical in light of the fact that males in Arab societies have the role of guardianship, bearing the burden of the family, and are preoccupied with finding suitable job opportunities to maintain the needs of their families. Males also suffer from the social, academic and professional stress that affects the level of consensus within them and with others, as well as their mindfulness, psychological resilience, awareness of their own competence, awareness of social support, sense of well-being and happiness, especially in light of the successive changes that prevailed in various aspects of life. On the other hand, females do not suffer the same stress and intensity level as males. They can express their negative feelings in front of others, and they can ask others to support them spiritually and morally, in contrast with males. If males try to seek others' help or support, this will undermine their manhood. Therefore, the females participants in the study showed higher signs of mindfulness, psychological resilience, self-efficacy, social support and happiness than males .

The results of the third hypothesis are consistent with the results of the Charlimeragn and Cotton's (2003) study that found a positive correlation between the number of hours of internet use and psychological well-being. These results indicate that the number of hours of internet use affect the scores of mental health components. As a result, the highest rate of internet use are the highest in the mean of mental health levels of mindfulness, psychological resilience, self-efficacy, awareness of social support and happiness for those with a low number of internet hours use (less than 3 hours a day). This corresponds to the nature of today's society and the reality of the lives of individuals. The research sample reveals a high level of stress, which leads people to seek refuge within the internet and spend their free time away from reality, as well as their families and community control. Individuals today live in an environment that provides them with the technological life requirements of modern computers and smart phones that enables them to use social networking sites through time or space without restriction. This hypothesis demonstrated that those who use the internet moderately for a number of hours (3-6

hours) have obtained higher mental health scores than those who use the internet for less than three hours or those who use it for more than 6 hours.

Based on this analysis, we can conclude that the optimum use of internet is between 3 to 6 hours as a mean for psychological therapy. This mean can be viewed as a modern strategy in the light of Glasser's theory of positive addiction to reduce symptoms of mental illness among individuals of different age groups. Thus, if Glasser's ideas are used in regards to negative and positive addiction, and the consequences of vulnerability, and negative addiction is tackled, the individual's mental state can be strengthened in order to fight the problems he/ she faces in his/ her life. The use of the internet as a positive addiction to many people of this century can be used to outline the programs of building the strength necessary for the individual to cope with the challenges of life as a proposed approach to counseling and psychotherapy.

The results of the fourth hypothesis showed that several programs and means of social communication used by the individual could increase mindfulness, psychological resilience, self-efficacy, perception of social support and happiness. While increasing in the number of sites used for social communication, can increase feelings of comfort, enjoyment, acceptance, respect, appreciation and support, which increases the confidence of the individual himself/ herself and others. The increase in the number of sites, programs and means of social communication increases the cognitive enrichment of the individual and provides him/ her with greater opportunities to engage in reading, research and facilitate work through websites. Online social networking also allows individuals to strengthen their relationships with their family members within and outside their country. Therefore, this increases the individual's happiness, psychological resilience and his/ her awareness of efficiency as a person and ability to communicate, work, research, as well as increase his/ her knowledge and openness to others.

The result of the fifth hypothesis referred that the age group of 30 years is more intelligent, aware and positive than the age groups of less than 30 years. Among these age groups, the

negative manifestations of internet addiction may spread from anxiety, depression and isolation. The 30-year-old group of peoples and adults, use the internet effectively to read, research, work or for meaningful social communication and not for leisure. They are more satisfied with their use of the internet and are more mentally alert than those younger than 30 years of age. They are also more flexible, self-sufficient and more responsive to the support of others, as well as having a higher welfare and happiness, reaching a level of emotional, mental, moral, spiritual and mental maturity than those younger ages.

The results of the sixth hypothesis indicated significant statistical differences in the mean scores of mental health components (dimensions and scores) due to the use of the internet. The differences were for the benefit of the sample members who use the internet for the purpose of social communication. Ratios of 42.223, 41.735, 41.618, 41.688, 40.923, 208.188 respectively were higher than the mean of the internet users for the purpose of reading, research, and work. The results of the «Scheffe» about comparisons between the mean scores in the components of mental health (dimensions and total score) according to the purpose of using internet were shown. The results of this hypothesis are consistent with the results of Charlimoragn and Cotton (2003); Kalpidus, Costin and Morris (2011); Chen (2012); and Wang, Chau and Stefanone (2015) and show a positive relationship between the use of the internet for the purpose of social communication with psychological well-being.

Therefore, the planning of counseling programs based on the use of the internet for the purpose of social communication as one of the positive addictions referred to by Glasser is a necessity. This is a recent approach in counseling and psychotherapy to decrease the psychological problems of different age groups by improving the components of mental health.

Conclusion

In summary, the present study examined the components of mental health on a sample of internet users. Future researches should investigate the effectiveness of applied counseling

and psychotherapy interventions designed to increase mental health components and improved performance, well-being and relieve psychological disorder symptoms. In this regard also, more researches are needed to examine the effectiveness of the use of the positive internet addiction as a therapeutic approach to mental disorders, and plan programs based on Glasser's theory of positive addiction to increase the mental health components.

References

1. Abdullah, M. (2008). *Introduction to Mental Health*. (4th ed), Amman: Dar Al Fikr for Publishing and Distribution.
2. Abdul-Salam, N. (1998). Patterns and motivations of Egyptian youth 's use of the Internet: exploratory study. *Fourth Scientific Conference of the Faculty of Media, Cairo University on: Media and Youth Issues*. 85-.119
3. Abu Makarem, F. (2007). Nonconformistic behaviors and knowledge associated with Internet addiction. *Journal of Arab Studies in Psychology*, 6 (4), 85.137-
4. Al-Goma, S (2014). Internet addiction and its relationship to some personality disorders. *Journal of the Faculty of Arts, Beni Suef University*, 30, 180.210-
5. Al-Hilaa, M. (2000). The impact of home use of the Internet on the educational achievement of its users. *Arab Journal of Education*, 20 (2), 150.169-
6. Al-Kandari, Y. and Al-Qashan, H (2001). *Journal of Human and Social Sciences*, Kuwait, 1 (17), 1.45-
7. Al-Tarawneh, N. and Al-Fnaikh, L. (2012). The use of the Internet and its relation to academic achievement, social adjustment, depression and communication skills among the students of Qassim University. *Journal of the Islamic University for Educational and Psychological Studies*, 1 (20), 238.331-
8. Arnout, B. (2006). Internet addiction and its relationship to both personal dimensions and mental disorders in adolescents. *Journal of Faculty of Education, Zagazig University, Egypt*, 55, 33.96-
9. Ayazra, W. and Al-Malki. (2017) The Impact of Internet Use on Depression among Students of Parallel Program at King Saud University. *International Journal of Educational and Psychological Studies*, 1 (3), 309- 342.
10. Azab, H. (2001). Internet addiction and its relation to some dimensions of mental health among high school students (the flip side of the revolution of the nose), *the annual scientific conference of children and the environment*, 2425- March, Cairo, Egypt.
11. Chan, M.(2015). Mobile phone and the good life: Examining the relationships among mobile use, social capital and subjective well-being *New Media and Society*, 17(1), 96113-.
12. Charlimorgan, D. and Cotton, S.(2003). The relationships between internet activities and depressive symptoms in a sample of college freshman. *Cyber psychology Behavior and Social Networking*, 6(2), 133142-.
13. Chen, S.(2012).Internet use and psychological well-being among college students: A latent profile approach. *Computers in human Behavior*, 28, 22192226-.
14. Glasser, W.(1985). *Positive addiction*. New York: Harper Row.
15. Griffiths, M (1997). Psychology of computer use. Some comments on addiction use of the internet by Young(comments). *Psychological Reports*, 80, 8182-.
16. Al-Hantouchi, M. (2010). *Internet addiction among high school students in Riyadh: its prevalence, determinants, and relationship to depression*. Master Thesis (unpublished), Saudi Commission for Health Specialties, Saudi Arabia.
17. Kalpidous, M, Costin, D and Morris, J.(2011).The relationship between Facebook and well-being of undergraduate college students. *Cyber psychology Behavior and Social Networking*, 14(4), 183188-.

18. Khalidi, A. (2002). *Reference in mental health*. Cairo: The Arab House for Publishing and Distribution.
19. Majali, F. (2007). The use of the Internet and its impact on social relations among university youth: a field study. *Al-Manara Magazine*, 7 (13), 160- 193.
20. Mansour, T. (2004). Using the internet and its motivations among the students of the University of Bahrain: A field study, *The Arab Journal of Human Sciences*, 22 (86), 167196-.
21. Al-Qarni, M. (2011). Internet addiction and its relation to some psychological disorders in a sample of students of King Abdul Aziz University. *Journal of Faculty of Education*, Mansoura University, Egypt, 3 (75), 99.137-
22. Shaw, L. and Gant, L.(2002).In defense of internet : the relationship between internet communication and depression, loneliness, self-esteem and perceived social support. *Cyber Psychology and behavior*, 5, 157171-.
23. Sheikh, H. (2011). Internet addiction and its relation to some forms of harmonic behavior among secondary school students - descriptive study applied to Ahmed Zewail secondary school in Desouk. *Journal of Studies in Social Work and Human Sciences*, Egypt, 31 (3), 1021- 1072.
24. Shotton, M.(1991).The costs and benefits of computer addiction. *Behavior and information Technology*,10,219230-.
25. Taya, S. (2000). Internet in the Arab World: A Field Study on a Sample of Arab Youth. *Egyptian Journal of Public Opinion Research*, 4, 33.68-
26. Wang, W.,Chau, V.andStefanone, M.(2015). Socialties,ComunicationChannels,and personal well-being: study of the network lives of college students in Singapore. *American Behavior Scientist*,59(5),11891202-.
27. Zahran, H. (2005). *Mental Health and Psychotherapy*. (5th ed), Cairo: The World of Books.